

Abstract

Exploratory Data Analysis to Identify the Relationship between Depression-Anxiety and Spiritual-Religious Factors among Undergraduate Students

Nora Cuevas-Cuevas^{1,*} and Esperanza Carolina Orozco-del-Castillo²

¹ Tecnológico Nacional de México/Instituto Tecnológico de Mérida

² Centro de Investigación y de Estudios Avanzados del Instituto Politécnico Nacional

* Correspondence: nora.cc@merida.tecnm.mx

Abstract: The 3.8% of the world population is affected by depression [1] which is considered the most common precursor to suicide [2]. In Mexico, suicide is a public health problem. Yucatan had a national rate of 10.2 suicides per 100,000 persons [3]. The PHQ-9 is a nine item self-report questionnaire which provides a depression score. On the other hand, the GAD-7 is a seven item self-report questionnaire whose purpose is to measure GAD. These questionnaires, along with a spiritual/religious self-conception survey, were applied to 160 undergraduate students. EDA was used in order to establish data patterns and data relationships [4]. Univariate and multivariate analysis demonstrate how information behaves and correlates. As part of the EDA, it was decided to use a quartile approach with the aim of balancing the number of students per class of depression and anxiety level. We observed that, consistently with what is usually reported in the literature, depression and anxiety are highly correlated (0.96). More so, there appears to be an inversely proportional relationship between depression/anxiety and spiritual/religious self-conceptions, with the exception of high anxiety individuals, who seem to be more associated with a highly spiritual self-conception (as opposite to a high religious one).

Keywords: Depression; Anxiety; Spirituality/Religiosity

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by an Institutional Review Board of the Departamento de Sistemas y Computación of the Tecnológico Nacional de México/IT de Mérida.

Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

Acknowledgments: The authors thank the AAAIMX student chapter and MAIA platform for the support to collect the data used in this work.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Citation: Cuevas-Cuevas;
Orozco-del-Castillo . *ICAIMH Abstract
Proceedings 2023*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7955536>

Published: February, 2023

Copyright: © 2023 by the authors.
(CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

References

1. World Health Organization. Depression, 2021.
2. France, D.J.; Shiavi, R.G. Acoustical properties of speech as indicators of depression and suicidal risk. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* 2000, 47, 829–837. <https://doi.org/10.1109/10.846676>.
3. Peña, Y.O.; Pech, M.G.A.; Angulo, E.M.R. Self-Esteem, in Students of Yucatan, Mexico. *Psychology* 2019, 10, 411–423. <https://doi.org/10.4236/psych.2019.104028>.
4. Panda, B.; Panigrahi, C.R.; Pati, B. Exploratory Data Analysis and Sentiment Analysis of Drug Reviews 2022. 26, 1181–1189. <https://doi.org/10.13053/CyS-26-3-4093>.

Disclaimer/Publisher’s Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of AAAI, AAAIMX and/or the editor(s). AAAI, AAAIMX and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.